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D1.6 Interim report on communication and dissemination

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Lead partner for this deliverable: EMPIRICA

Authors:

Jessica Paul-Mesch EMPIRICA
Asha Patel EMPIRICA

Contributors:

Farah Diehl-Fahim EMPIRICA
Griselda Marku EMPIRICA

Peer Reviewers:

Dipak Kalra IHD
Juan Carlos Rejón Parrilla FPS

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Abstract

This deliverable details how D1.5 Communication and Dissemination Plan, delivered in Month 6 of the project, has been put into action in the 12 months that followed. In particular, it focuses on what has been disseminated, through which channels and methods, and the stakeholders that were targeted. As this deliverable marks the midpoint of the ASSESS DHT project, it also provides a point of reflection for adaptations to the Communication and Dissemination strategy going forward.

Statement of originality

This deliverable contains original unpublished work except where clearly indicated otherwise. Acknowledgement of previously published material and of the work of others has been made through appropriate citation, quotation or both. Views and opinions expressed are those of the author(s) only and do not necessarily reflect those of HaDEA. Neither the European Union nor the granting authority can be held responsible for them.

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EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

This deliverable details how D1.5 Communication and Dissemination Plan, delivered in Month 6 of the project, has been put into action in the 12 months that followed. In particular, it focuses on what has been disseminated, through which channels and methods, and the stakeholders that were targeted. As this deliverable marks the midpoint of the ASSESS DHT project, it also provides a point of reflection for adaptations to the Communication and Dissemination strategy going forward. In doing so, it provides an overview of the milestone campaigns, which constitute the centre of the communication and dissemination strategy of ASSESS DHT. It also highlights examples of additional communication and dissemination activities and details an initial quantitative and qualitative evaluation of the activities undertaken so far. The one aspect which was not part of the original communications plan, but is being accomplished rather well, are academic publications, which serve as an additional channel towards the academic community and others. It is concluded that a strong base was established to continue the activities, and that the focus of the external communication and dissemination will shift from the establishment of an overall project identity online and in person to promoting the project's outputs and fostering sustainability as ASSESS DHT advances.

1 Introduction

This deliverable, D1.6 Interim report on communication and dissemination, builds on D1.5 Communication and dissemination plan. As such, it details the execution of this plan throughout the first 18 months of the ASSESS DHT project. The deliverable is structured as follows: this chapter presents an overview of the scope and objectives of this deliverable. Chapter 2 presents an overview of the milestone campaigns that were executed and those that are planned. Chapter 3 details the communication and dissemination activities that were conducted in addition to the milestone campaigns. Chapter 4 presents an initial quantitative evaluation of the internal and external communication endeavours of ASSESS DHT. Finally, chapter 5 provides reflections on the execution of the communication and dissemination plan thus far and presents an outlook on future activities.

1.1 Scope and objectives of this deliverable

At month 18, this deliverable marks the midpoint of the lifetime of the ASSESS DHT project. As such, the objectives of this deliverable are two-fold: firstly, it sets out to reflect on the achievement of the implemented communication and dissemination strategy which was established in D1.5 at month six of the project. Secondly, it provides a basis for an outlook and improvement of the future communication and dissemination strategy and activities of ASSESS DHT.

In doing so, this deliverable focuses primarily on the external communication and dissemination endeavours of the project. However, Chapter 4.1 provides insights into some of the internal communication and dissemination activities undertaken in ASSESS DHT.

D1.5 summarised the overarching aim of ASSESS DHT's dissemination activities as follows: "to secure HTA agency endorsement and to foster the developer's understanding of the assessment framework put forward by the project"¹. In working towards this aim, four dissemination objectives were defined which are presented in the box below.

Dissemination Objectives (DO)

- **DO1. Raise awareness:** Engage with stakeholders and raise awareness about the necessity of harmonising different DHT approaches to assessment and the benefits of mutual assessments recognised across settings and countries. Advocate for adoption of such approaches and encourage key players, especially HTA bodies, to join the work and use the framework and tools produced in the project.
- **DO2. Engagement of key stakeholders:** Continuously engage and create opportunities for receiving input, delivering information and ensuring adoption among relevant stakeholders.
- **DO3. Scientific publications, posters and participation in conferences:** Promote the scientific work, especially from WPs 2 and 3, to a wider audience and ensure it is well understood and accepted.
- **DO4. Post-project action planning to facilitate future uptake of ASSESS DHT results:** Think about next steps beyond the project and address points of sustainability, incl. how the tools are to be used (e.g. licensing), what training can be offered in the future, what capacities are required, etc.

¹ ASSESS DHT D1.5 Communication and dissemination plan, p.7

2 Milestone campaigns

As laid out in D1.5 Communication and dissemination plan, the core of the external communication and dissemination strategy of ASSESS DHT consists of the foreseen milestone campaigns. In its description of action, the project defined nine project milestones, each marking either key content-related achievements of the project or highlighting the execution of essential project operations.

D1.5 defined both the timing, as well as example messages of the milestone campaigns. After careful consideration, the work conducted in the execution of the communication and dissemination plan (1.5, executed in the scope of T1.6) deviates slightly from laid out plan. The reasoning for this is that the timing for the campaigns suggested in D1.5 coincided with the actual achievement of the Milestones. While this works well for internal communication and dissemination activities, the campaigns focus on external communication and some time for internal digestion and discussion of new achievements had to be allowed before communicating said achievements externally. As a result, the ASSESS DHT communication team aimed to provide clear messages to external audiences and avoid communicating project contents prematurely.

2.1 Realised milestone campaigns

In total, three milestone campaigns were realised thus far. To summarise central activities in relation to these campaigns, and the materials developed, this sub-chapter will present the rationale for each campaign, the stakeholders that were targeted, and the channels through which this was done. Moreover, the materials that were developed for each campaign are highlighted.

2.1.1 Milestone 1: All project enabling resources are operational (M6)

Milestone 1 “All project enabling resources are operational” includes aspects such as the project website, quality plan and handbook. It was completed in M6. The communication goal in relation to this milestone was initially phrased as “Inform stakeholders that ASSESS DHT has successfully established all necessary resources to support the project [...]”². This goal has since been redefined; however, the original phrasing of the goal has been helpful to guide project internal communication. As the consortium consists of many individuals, project-internal communication on this milestone has proven vital to ensure all project members are aware of the core project resources. However, it was reflected that the only project-enabling resource of interest to project-external audiences was the project website, and by extend its social media presence on X and LinkedIn, as it serves as a point of information on project activities. This led to a shift in focus of this Milestone campaign.

The targeted stakeholder groups of this milestone campaign were broad and aimed to address all stakeholder groupings identified in D1.5 (Users of DHTs, Developers of DHTs, researchers, governing bodies, and financiers). As a result, this campaign aimed at widespread yet generic messages on LinkedIn, X (formerly Twitter) and the project website. Additionally, a communication package was provided to project partners and discussed at the virtual Communication Office Team (vCOT) meeting to encourage consortium members to either share social media posts created by the official ASSESS DHT accounts to their professional or organisation profiles, or to create their own.

The communication package, and excerpt of which is illustrated in Figure 1, was disseminated to all project partners. It contained suggestions for social media posts to share on X and LinkedIn, as well as for a website news item. Moreover, it entailed suggestions for visuals to be used. In doing so, the package aims to alleviate the burden on individual partners to create their own communication materials, thus encouraging them to post on this topic and ensuring that the posts that were issued

² ASSESS DHT D1.5 Communication and dissemination plan, p. 10

were aligned with the visual identity of the ASSESS DHT project brand. These materials were found to be helpful, and as a result, several project partners posted both news items on their website, as well as social media posts.

Figure 1. Communication package provided to the consortium members for the promotion of Milestone 1

Figure 2 illustrates one of several visuals that were created to promote the launch of the ASSESS DHT website. It aims to encourage people to visit the project website and create overall awareness of the project. In doing so, it also presents a stepping stone in establishing ASSESS DHT as a recognisable project brand.

Figure 2. Visual for advertising ASSESS DHT's website launch on social media (X, LinkedIn)

2.1.2 Milestone 2: Call for tender for a case study on assessment of an AI-based technology used in radiology (M20)

Milestone 2 marks the publication of the ASSESS DHT call for tender for a case study on assessment of an AI-based technology used in radiology. The rationale for this publication is to formulate a call to action for software development companies who have an appropriate technology in their portfolio to apply to this call for tender. As a secondary impact, the campaign also aims to create interest in its case studies that will apply the HTA framework developed by the project.

As the initial period set for the open call (March to May, 2025, extended until June) yielded no suitable technologies for piloting, it was decided to re-launch the open call from June 20 to July 25, 2025. The overall campaign was published on X, LinkedIn, the ASSESS DHT website via the news item, as well as a newsletter post.

Figure 3 illustrates the preview of the call for tender on the ASSESS DHT website. These news items aimed to summarise all information on the call for tender at a glance for visitors to the website. Moreover, the inclusion of keywords in these news items aimed to improve the SEO of the website to push the website in relevant search results.

Figure 3. Call for tender for an AI-based technology in radiology on the ASSESS DHT website

In addition to the news items, the open call was highlighted in the header of the ASSESS DHT website (Figure 4), thus giving the call a high visibility on the website. On this page, all information on the call was summarised, and the call documents are available for download.

Figure 4. Call for tender for an AI-based technology in radiology highlighted in the header of the ASSESS DHT website (highlight added)

Figure 5 highlights the contents of the subpage on the ASSESS DHT Call for AI-based technology used in radiology that users reach when clicking on the “open call” button.

ASSESS DHT Call for Artificial Intelligence-based technology used in radiology

ASSESS DHT is calling for an organisation which has developed an AI-based digital health technology (DHT) used in the radiology domain. If selected, the DHT developer will have the opportunity to pilot the ASSESS DHT assessment framework by undergoing a simulated health technology assessment (HTA).

Why should you apply?

If you have an AI-based DHT in the radiology domain used for image analysis with CE-marking or at an advanced stage of regulatory approval, you can benefit from being among the pioneer technology providers in Europe who will test the ASSESS DHT assessment framework. You will interact with the Health Technology Assessment bodies in the project and learn about the HTA process. You will receive funding of €86,000 for your efforts.

How can you submit an application?

The call will be open in the period 20 June – 25 July 2025. Only one applicant will be selected.

The call documents can be downloaded after filling in the short form below. The zip file contains a PDF file with instructions and a Microsoft Word form for the application.

Firstname *

Lastname *

Email *

I am interested to learn about the scope of the call and the submission process

I intend to submit an application for this call

Send & download call documents

Figure 5. Open call sub-page on the ASSESS DHT website

Figure 6 contains example posts on this milestone that were posted on the ASSESS DHT LinkedIn account. The visuals created aimed to summarise at a glance the key benefits for software developers to participate in the call for tender and encourage them to take action. The accompanying text (Figure 7) provided additional information, such as basic information on the contents of the project. As can be seen in the example of Figure 6, the posts on the call for tender were shared comparatively often. Additionally, LinkedIn members also commented on posts related to the call for tender, tagging other users to encourage them to check the post. As such a widely shared post, it was expected that it would be seen by people who were not yet familiar with the ASSESS DHT project and its aims. This is why a short summary on the project was provided directly in the post text, and links to the website were provided. Moreover, the consortium partner organisations were tagged to encourage them to repost the posts, and to showcase the organisations behind the project. It was assumed that in addition to the EU and UKRI funding disclaimers in the text and the logos on the visuals, this would showcase the credibility of the project. The use of emoticons and bold visuals aimed to draw the attention of LinkedIn users to these posts.

Figure 6. Example posts Milestone 2 on LinkedIn

Figure 7. Example text LinkedIn post on Milestone 2

Figure 8 shows an example of a post on X on the Call for tender. Texts on X are characterised by containing only few characters. Given these limitations, the text and visuals aimed to raise the interest of potential applicants to follow the link to the ASSESS DHT website to receive more information. As with the LinkedIn post, the use of emoticons and bold visuals aimed to get X users attention.

Figure 8. Example post Milestone 2 on X

To ensure the widest possible reach of this campaign, a communications package to be used by the consortium was created. It consisted of post suggestions for X and LinkedIn, as well as accompanying visuals. Additionally, an email template was created to encourage the consortium to share the open call to their networks. An excerpt of the communication package is highlighted in Figure 9. This communication package, as all others, follows the same structure to allow project partners to find the information they are looking for quickly as they are already familiar with this document template. However, in the more recent communication packages, a specific team member rather than project partner (empirica) was added as a contact for any questions. This allowed for stronger recognisability for responsibilities within the consortium and encouraged consortium members to contact this team member directly with any open questions or ideas they had.

Dear partners,

To support the public re-launch of the ASSESS DHT open call for AI-based technologies used in radiology we put at your disposal a communications package that includes the following:

- A set of **social media** posts and visuals to share on X and LinkedIn (feel free to adapt these texts to other social media platforms), so you can spread the word about the website launch.

Please use these materials to **help us promote the open call for technologies in AI in radiology**. If you have any questions or suggestions, please contact [redacted] from the empirica team [redacted]

Thank you for your support!

ASSESS DHT social media accounts to tag:

- ▶ Website link: www.assess-dht.eu
- ▶ Social media accounts: [Twitter](#) and [LinkedIn](#)

1. Social media

**Note*: You can post directly on your social media channels (please tag ASSESS DHT X/LinkedIn) or repost from the ASSESS DHT channels. Feel free to adapt the texts to your communications style and audience.*

Links to interact with our posts:

- ▶ [X/Twitter](#)
- ▶ [LinkedIn](#)

Please use the hashtag #ASSESSDHT when posting about the project. This helps us interact and track posts for reporting.

a. X (formerly Twitter), BlueSky

CALL RE-LAUNCHED!

#ASSESSDHT is reopening its open call for **AI-based digital health tech in radiology!**

	CALL	RE-LAUNCHED!
New deadline:	25 July	2025, 17:00 CET

<https://assess-dht.eu/call-radiology/>

RT or tag any AI-in-radiology innovators—let's shape the future of digital health together!

b. LinkedIn

🔥 Radiology AI innovators – don't miss this! 🔥

The ASSESS DHT open call is still live! We're looking for AI-powered, CE-marked (or nearly there) image-analysis technologies in radiology.

👉 What's ASSESS DHT all about?

We're a European initiative building a harmonised, trustworthy HTA framework for Digital Health Technologies—making it easier for health systems and patients across Europe to adopt innovations.

👉 Who should apply?

Organizations with AI-based DHTs in imaging (radiology) that are CE-marked or close to regulatory approval. Eligible solutions must perform automated analysis of radiological image data (pixels or embeddings). Tools that only process text, metadata or referral information are not within scope. The selected team will pilot our framework via a simulated HTA, gaining exclusive insights into Europe's evaluation processes.

👉 Benefits at a glance

- Become a European pioneer in HTA assessment
- Engage with HTA bodies across the continent

Figure 9. Excerpt of the communication package on Milestone 2 provided to the consortium

In addition to social media and the ASSESS DHT project website, the call was also advertised via the ASSESS DHT newsletter. A preview of the newsletter is displayed below.

Figure 10. Preview open call newsletter

Out of 56 subscribers, 62,50 % opened the newsletter, and it had a click rate of 22,86 %.

2.1.3 Milestone 3: Taxonomy developed and presented to external experts for feedback (M10)

The communication and dissemination activities related to Milestone 3, Taxonomy developed and presented to external experts for feedback, contribute to DO2. Engagement of key stakeholders in particular. To gather sufficient feedback from experts for this Milestone and the overall activities in the project, a Call for Experts was published on the ASSESS DHT website and social media (Figure 11; Figure 12).

📅 18 March 2024

Calls for Expert Input to Develop Assessment Frameworks for Digital Health Technologies

As a European project dedicated to advancing the adoption of Digital Health Technologies (DHTs) across the continent, we issue a call for experts to contribute to the development of assessment...

[read more](#)

Figure 11. Call for experts for feedback to the ASSESS DHT taxonomy on the ASSESS DHT website

Figure 12. Visual for call for experts for social media

Additionally, expert feedback to the taxonomy was gathered via the first sustainability roundtable (WP6), which was hosted in November 2024 by ASSESS DHT. Sister-project EDiHTA was invited to present alongside ASSESS DHT (Figure 13 below).

Figure 13. Sustainability Roundtable with EDiHTA, Recap on LinkedIn

2.2 Outstanding milestone campaigns

As detailed in the introduction of this chapter, not all of the milestones that were formally completed have been communicated externally yet. This is due to the fact that the achievement of a milestone does not necessarily mark the end of project internal discourse. To promote clarity in external messaging, the following milestones are currently in the pipeline for publication of appropriate campaigns:

- Milestone 4: Initial version of manual piloting assessment methods for digital health technologies (M15)
- Milestone 5: Initial versions of all data related criteria ready for inclusion in our framework (M12)
- Milestone 6: Initial version of life-cycle assessment of DHT (M18)
- Milestone 7: European tool to optimise approach to addressing gaps in evidence development plans (M18).

In preparation for the open consultations and stakeholder engagement activities foreseen within the scope of WP6, the project communication campaigns going forward will focus on the contents of these milestones to ensure stakeholder awareness of project achievements. These campaigns will be created in collaboration with the respective teams working on the content associated with the milestones laid out above. They will be based upon the communication and dissemination strategy laid out in D1.5.

Moreover, the following milestones have not yet been reached, and will be communicated on as they are achieved:

- Milestone 8: Launch Open call for evidence submissions to gather feedback on usability of outputs (M20)
- Milestone 9: ASSESS DHT Repository is online (M28).

3 Additional communication and dissemination activities

In addition to the milestone campaigns, several other communication and dissemination activities were conducted. Some of these activities, like the partners campaign in which the consortium partners were highlighted, were already reported on in D1.5 Communication and dissemination plan.

Within the first 18 months of the project, the focus of the communication and dissemination strategy of ASSESS DHT was to raise the **overall visibility of the project** and to establish the project brand online and offline. To do so, several posts highlighting the consortium as such were generated. For example, posts on the face-to-face project-internal meetings, such as the Vienna consortium meeting in the summer of 2025 Figure 14, were created.

Figure 14. Vienna consortium meeting 2025 example post on LinkedIn

Moreover, the international collaboration and involvement and consideration of key stakeholders are promoted via various social media posts, as highlighted in Figure 15 and Figure 16, respectively.

Figure 15. Consortium partners presence across Europe post on LinkedIn

Figure 16. Stakeholder collaboration post on LinkedIn

To contribute to **DO1. Raise awareness**, different facets of the added value the ASSESS DHT project provides, namely the creation of a harmonised approach towards DHT assessment, were highlighted across multiple social media posts. In doing so, ASSESS DHT published targeted content on LinkedIn and X to engage key stakeholders' groups and a general audience. These were designed to raise awareness of the project and its value proposition in a clear and accessible format. Each post was supported with consistent visual and links to the project.

A visual and captioned post (Figure 17) on manufacturer addressed challenges this group faces without a harmonised approach towards assessing DHTs, such as inconsistent HTA criteria and high evidence generation costs. It Introduced European repository as a solution for streamlining evidence submission.

Figure 17. LinkedIn post of challenges and solution for DHT developers and manufacturers

A post (Figure 18) aimed at clinical experts highlighted the critical role of clinical expertise in HTA, especially in low-evidence or complex areas. It emphasised the importance of clinician engagement to ensure fair and robust assessment methodologies.

Figure 18. Engaging clinical experts in the HTA process post on LinkedIn

To raise awareness around how ASSESS DHT fits into the European regulatory developments relevant to the project, a LinkedIn post (Figure 19) communicated the entry into force of the HTAR and highlighted the projects 'contributions to supporting its implementation.

Figure 19. EU HTAR post on LinkedIn

ASSESS DHT engaged in external-facing communications that highlighted its scientific contribution and methodological insights through participation in expert events, webinar, and conference, thus contributing to DO3. Such as promotional post for the HTA- focused for example on the participation in a webinar hosted by WHO Europe and NICE on 27th May 2025, where the ASSESS DHT methodological framework was presented (see Figure 20). Further examples of communication activities on ASSESS DHT’s contributions to the scientific discourse through participation in high level conference and expert meetings include posts on the project’s participation in ISPOR (Figure 21) and the MedTech Forum (Figure 22).

Figure 20. Webinar highlighting ASSESS DHT project example post on LinkedIn

Figure 21. Participation post at ISPOR poster session on LinkedIn on the (left) and on X on the (right)

Figure 22. ASSESS DHT at the MedTech Forum 2025 post on LinkedIn

Project communication further highlighted scientific articles either published in the scope of the project, or of relevance to the ASSESS DHT audience, thus contributing to the overall scientific discourse. Examples of such posts are presented in Figure 23 and Figure 24, respectively

Figure 23. Recommended reading on DHT regulation and reimbursement posted on X

Figure 24. Recommendation reading on assessment of digital medical devices posted on LinkedIn

Together, these activities contributed meaningfully by communicating and disseminating project knowledge through formal scientific platforms and strengthening the credibility and uptake of its outputs.

4 Monitoring and reporting indicators and evaluation

This chapter presents an overview of the monitoring and reporting indicators and evaluation at the midpoint of the lifetime of the ASSESS DHT project. In doing so, it is differentiated between an overview of internal communication and dissemination activities, and external communication and dissemination activities.

4.1 Internal communication and dissemination activities overview

The table below gives a complete overview of internal meetings to the ASSESS DHT project. These meetings are an integral part of the internal communication and dissemination strategy, ensuring alignment across the consortium, and fostering cross-WP synergies.

Table 1. Summary of recurring meetings

Type of Meeting	Frequency	Place	Organiser
PEC	Monthly	Online	EMPIRICA
vCOT	Monthly	Online	EMPIRICA
WP	Monthly	Online	EMPIRICA/WP Leads
Full consortium	Every 8 to 9 months	Online/In-person	EMPIRICA

The Project Executive Committee (PEC) is scheduled as a regular monthly meeting. As laid out in D1.3 Project Handbook, it is “Composed of Project Coordination team and Work Package Leaders, responsible for technical and operational management, compliance with ethical standards and data protection regulation, quality, risk mitigation and progress tracking”³. It serves as a central forum for discussing managerial and content-related transversal issues.

The virtual Communication Office Team (vCOT) is scheduled as a regular monthly meeting. The invitees to this meeting are communication experts and consortium members of each consortium partner. As established in D1.3 Project Handbook and D1.5 Communication and dissemination plan, it serves as a central platform for discussion of external communication and dissemination activities of the project.

Individual Work Package (WP) meetings were established for various WPs in accordance with their needs and project timelines. These meetings allow for specific WP-related discussions and are a touchpoint between WP members. The meetings are led by the respective WP leads.

Full consortium meetings are scheduled to take place at least once every 8 to 9 months, both online and in-person. These meetings provide a vital opportunity for in-depth personal discussions of project content.

In addition to these recurring meetings, additional meetings may be organised for internal communication purposes as needed. For example, in the first half of 2025, several cross-WP meetings on the User Manual took place to ensure alignment on its various sections.

In addition to the various meeting formats utilised within the consortium, ASSESS DHT also utilises a dedicated Microsoft Teams space for internal communications, and announcements, as well as

³ D1.3 Project Handbook, p.12

working jointly on documents. This is supplemented by communication and dissemination via email, for which distribution lists have been established.

4.2 External communication and dissemination overview

The table below lays out the specific impact indicators that ASSESS DHT collects to measure the success of the project's external communication and dissemination efforts across various channels.

Table 2. Impact indicators for ASSESS DHT communication targets and achievements at the midpoint of the project runtime

Nr	Indicator	Method of Measurement	Target (to be achieved until M36)	Status as of M18
Website				
1	No. of unique visits to assess-dht.eu	Website statistics	10,000	5865
2	No. of new events published assess-dht.eu	Website statistics	6	1
3	No. of news published on assess-dht.eu	Website statistics	30	7
4	No. of unique visitors to the ASSESS DHT repository	Website statistics	<500	N/A
Social media				
5	No. of social media campaigns	Project reporting, D1.6, D1.7	12	4
6	No. of tweets using the hashtag #assessdht	X statistics	50	13
7	No. of X accounts using the hashtag #assessdht	Hashtag tracking statistics	10	5
8	No. of followers of the project's X account	X statistics	200	39
9	No. of tweets by project account	X statistics	250	61
10	No. of followers of the project's LinkedIn page	LinkedIn statistics	800	453
11	No. of LinkedIn accounts using the hashtag #assessdht	Hashtag tracking statistics	100	9
12	No. of LinkedIn posts by project account	LinkedIn statistics	250	84
13	Post/tweet impression rate by the projects accounts	Project reporting, D1.6, D1.7	10%	7.7%/6%*
Dissemination materials				
14	No. of explanatory dissemination materials included in the ASSESS DHT repository, addressing various groups (at least decision-makers, health professionals, public)	Project reporting, D1.7	3	N/A
(Scientific) publications				
15	No. of academic and other scientific publications, open access white papers and position papers	Project reporting, D1.6, D1.7	6	11
*Please note that advanced analytics for X (formerly Twitter) are now only available for Premium users. Hence, the engagement rate only reflects the timeframe from March until April 2024.				

5 Reflections, outlook and conclusion

The previous chapter laid out the communication and dissemination activities undertaken on the basis of D1.5 Communication and dissemination plan. It can be concluded that while the Milestone campaigns slightly deviate from what was originally envisaged in terms of their timing, the activities successfully created visibility of the project via its website and social media accounts. The overview of activities presented in this deliverable further highlights the adaptive approach the communication and dissemination workstream of ASSESS DHT takes which is needed to reflect the dynamic needs of the project.

Thus far, the communication campaigns run by ASSESS DHT focused primarily on establishing overall visibility of the project and creating a recognisable project identity. Moreover, initial results of the project, including its taxonomy, as well as the establishment of its infrastructure including an extensive expert network, were key items the communication and dissemination efforts focused on.

The quantitative and qualitative insights of ASSESS DHT's communication activities within its first 18 months support the conclusion that the project has built a strong foundation of an engaged audience across channels that it can build on going forward. The focus of the next campaigns, particularly the milestones that will be targeted, have been presented in chapter 2.2. Additionally, the project will also focus increasingly on DO4, thus promoting the sustainability and uptake of the project outputs. In doing so, WP1 will collaborate with WP6 to ensure meaningful stakeholder engagement and an aligned external project communication.

The indicators presented in chapter 4 will be continued to be monitored throughout the course of the rest of the project and will be reported in D1.7 Final report on communication and dissemination impact [M36].

Overall, it was noted that since the start of the project, several research institutes and other relevant stakeholders within the ASSESS DHT network have left the platform X (formerly Twitter). To ensure the continued relevance of the communication and dissemination channels utilised, this shift will be monitored closely and alternative platforms, such as Bluesky, will be considered.